

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Organic and conventional farmers' experience with the application of different soil management practices in the Nemoral region

Sustainable soil management practices play a key role in addressing the soil degradation and soil fertility issues as well as in supporting the long-term economic performance of farms. The EU Soil Strategy for 2030 outlines various sustainable agricultural practices, such as organic production, agroforestry, cover cropping, reduced tillage, crop rotation, conversion to grassland, and other practices that would help maintain and restore soil health.

The questionnaire survey conducted in the SoilDiverAgro project focused on farmers' experience in and attitudes towards different practices. In the Nemoral region, 276 Estonian farmers answered the survey. Around one-third of responses were collected from the organic farmers.

The farmers were given a list of 13 agricultural practices and were asked to assess whether or not they had used those. The

most common practice was leaving the crop residues on the fields, as 80% of the farmers indicated that they are currently doing this. At present, half of the farmers used non-inversion tillage, large crop rotation in a 4-or-more-year cycle, and less frequent plowing. Around one-third of respondents mentioned using reduced tillage depths, mulching, and intercropping. Cover crops and catch crops were used by a quarter of all farmers. Agroforestry, hedgerows and grass strips, and no tillage were the least used management practices, as less than 20% of respondents were using those at present, and over half of the farmers also indicated that they do not have any kind of previous experience in applying those practices. In comparison with conventional farmers, the organic farmers were somewhat more likely to apply cover crops, catch crops, and agroforestry and less likely to use precision fertilization.

1. Biodiversity in the organic field; SoilDiverAgro CS12A in Tartu County; Nemoral region. Photo: Shanskiy, M.

KEYWORDS

Sustainable agriculture, soil health, Estonia, organic agriculture

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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